

ESM B

Protocol Amendments

Date of Amendment	Section of Change	Original	Revision	Rational
07/10/2023	Codebook	s_students: Share of <i>(undergraduate)</i> students	s_students: Share of undergraduate and graduate students	Most reports assessed the level of education rather than the proportion of undergraduate students. We argue that graduate participants are as unrepresentative of the general population as undergraduate students. The variable was broadened to avoid loss of information and to allow for the planned investigation of whether the discriminant validity of Disintegration is compromised by sample homogeneity due to academic education.
07/28/2023	Codebook		Added the number of items of HEXACO-PI-R and DELTA	This was necessary to compute the meta-analytically averaged reliability estimates.
07/31/2023	Data Extraction and Coding Procedure	'In the case of substantial data dependency, the intercorrelation matrices are averaged into a single matrix and the information	To check whether potential dependent effect sizes challenge the generalizability of the analysis, we	This allowed us to assess the impact of data dependency by comparing the full model to a restricted model that averaged multiple pieces of information.

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		is collected at the total sample level.’ (p. 8)	performed an additional sensitivity analysis with averaged effect sizes in case of multiple reported effect sizes.	
08/07/2023	Data Synthesis & Analysis Plan	OSMASEM (see p. 9)	OSMASEM was dropped in favor of the first step of TSSEM.	The OSMASEM did not converge because we did not specify a model structure. Thus, the only feasible MASEM approach was the first stage of TSSEM.
08/18/2023	Data Synthesis & Analysis Plan	OSMASEM moderator analysis (see p. 9)	Multivariate meta-regressions for each moderator	Stage 1 TSSEM does not allow for the testing of moderators. Jak & Cheung (2020) emphasized the possibility of multivariate meta-regressions to analyze moderators in Stage 1. This approach was feasible as the multivariate model did not differ at all from the metaSEM model.
08/20/2023	Sensitivity Analyses	Redo main analysis & moderator analysis while excluding DELTA-10	Instead of reconducting the moderator analysis, we modelled the DELTA version as a moderator.	Omitting the DELTA-10 samples would have resulted in a loss of information. However, we decided it would be more informative to see if certain intercorrelations were affected by the DELTA version.

Note. The protocol was preregistered on OSF on June 27, 2023. <https://osf.io/project/dz3mc/files/osfstorage/649b38a66c09810c127d174f>